

A High-Sensitivity Bi-modal Plasmo-photonic Refractive Index Sensor

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ABSTRACT: We present a new, ultra-compact bimodal interferometric plasmonic sensor integrated on a SU-8 photonic waveguide platform. Two access SU-8 photonic waveguides are separated by an aluminum-based stripe which resides on top of a thinner SU-8 waveguide layer. In this way, two metal/insulator interfaces are formed at the top and bottom metal surfaces which are capable of supporting two respective surface plasmon polariton (SPP) modes that are subsequently interfering at the output photonic waveguide. The upper metal surface is exposed to the surrounding medium and serves as the sensing element, while the lower surface serves as the reference branch of the interferometer. After a thorough optimization process, the device was fabricated and experimentally characterized. A clear bimodal interferometric response was obtained when the upper metallic surface was exposed to air and water, with both cases revealing an excellent agreement between the simulated and experimental values for the free spectral range. The experimental bulk refractive index sensitivity of the bimodal interferometer was evaluated by using water solutions on top of the upper metallic surface, demonstrating experimental sensitivity values of 4386 nm/RIU that are in good agreement with the value of 5806 nm/RIU expected from simulation. The proposed sensing device takes advantage of the polymeric material SU-8 for the photonic waveguide, reducing in this way fabrication time and overall fabrication cost.

KEYWORDS. Photonic integrated circuits, polymer, plasmonic sensors, aluminum, bimodal, refractive index.

Introduction

In recent years, integrated photonic sensors have attracted the interest of the scientific community due to their high-sensitivity credentials, real-time and label-free operation in combination with multiplexed capabilities and the potential of mass production at a low-cost. Photonic sensors typically rely on the evanescent wave detection mechanism that exploits the interaction between the evanescent field and the analyte residing on top of the transducing photonic waveguide [1]. Although this approach can lead to high bulk sensitivities values by properly engineering the sensor layout, the performance of integrated evanescent wave photonic sensors is limited by the partial

exposure of the propagating optical mode to the ambient environment (weak evanescent field). This necessitates the use of rather high sensing lengths that can often extend to several millimeters or even centimeters, restricting their potential for employment in field/point-of-care applications where sensor compactness and ease-of-use form critical factors. Single path or bimodal interferometers have been proposed as an alternative architectural scheme that can effectively collapse the interferometer into just a single waveguide [2] in order to reduce chip area requirements. Although promising sensitivity results have been reported, photonic bimodal interferometers still didn't manage to avoid the need for millimeter-scale sensing lengths in order to support compact sensing configurations.

Sensing length reduction can be only achieved by migrating into a waveguide technology that allows for enhanced light-

matter interaction. Plasmonics comprises a well-known waveguide platform that can inherently offer this property, natively supporting the profound SPP mode exposure to the liquid analyte that lies on top of the metallic waveguide. This has been already utilized in impressive experimental demonstrations, where chip-integrated all-plasmonic sensors allow for highly reliably and ultra-compact devices [3]. The selective co-integration of plasmonic structures within a low-loss photonic waveguide platform allowed to combine the high sensing capabilities of plasmons with the low-loss passive functionalities offered by photonics, leading to a new class of high-performance plasmo-photonic sensors. These have been demonstrated both in ring resonators [8]-9 and Mach-Zehnder Interferometric (MZI) [10] layouts, yielding ultra-compact and high-performance sensor circuitry and validating the increased benefits arising by the interplay of photonic interferometric arrangements with plasmonic sensing areas [12]. Plasmonic waveguide sensing elements have been also employed in single-arm Si or TiO₂-based bimodal interferometers towards optimizing footprint requirements both from an architectural and technological perspective, providing, however, rather moderate sensitivity values [16].

In this paper, we present an integrated plasmo-photonic bimodal interferometer that employs an aluminum plasmonic waveguide co-integrated onto a SU-8 photonic platform and exhibits almost double sensitivity among all bimodal refractive index plasmo-photonic sensors presented so far. Aluminum has been selected as a plasmonic material because it is an inexpensive and abundant material compared to noble metals, such as gold (Au) or silver (Ag), and even copper (Cu). At the same time, it retains significant SPP propagation lengths with our group's previous work [13] reporting an Al propagation length of 50 μm in aqueous environment at 1550 nm. On top of that, a native alumina layer (2-3 nm thick) is formed on the surface of Aluminum and protects it from further oxidization [19] in contrast to Cu that necessitates the deposition of additional

protective layers which limits its performance [20]. The main reason of the higher sensitivity response of the proposed device compared to other bimodal plasmonic sensors is the difference between the effective indexes of the used WGs, as explained also in [21]. Following their theoretical analysis, a series of plasmo-photonic bimodal interferometers with plasmonic waveguide lengths ranging between 25-150 μm was fabricated and characterized, with experimental results successfully validating the theoretical predictions. The plasmo-photonic bimodal configuration with a 100 μm long plasmonic waveguide sensing element was then also validated as a refractive index sensor, revealing an experimental sensitivity value up to 4386 nm/RIU that was found to be in good agreement with the corresponding simulation results. Besides the low coupling and propagation losses supported by SU-8 waveguides, the successful co-integration of plasmonics onto SU-8-based bimodal sensor layouts paves the inroad towards reduced overall fabrication cost and turn-around times compared to silicon-based CMOS compatible photonic waveguide platforms.

METHODS

Sensor layout and principle of operation

The 3D conceptual schematic of the proposed plasmo-photonic bimodal interferometric sensor is depicted in Figure 1(a), with its side- and top-view shown in Figure 1(b) and (c), respectively. The interferometric layout is formed by two access photonic SU-8 based waveguides (WGs) that are separated by an Aluminum (Al) metal stripe located on top of an SU-8 waveguide layer that is thinner than the two access waveguides, hereafter referred to as bottom SU-8 layer. In this way, two metal/insulator interfaces are formed at the top and bottom surfaces of the metal stripe and are able to support SPP modes. The top metallic surface is exposed to the surrounding medium (liquid sample) and, thus, serves as the sensing arm of the interferometric structure, while the bottom surface plays the role

Figure 1. (a) Conceptual 3D schematic of the bimodal plasmo-photonic refractive index sensor, (b), (c) side view and top view of the device, respectively, (d) cross section of the input SU-8 photonic WG along with the electric field distribution of the fundamental TM photonic mode (e) cross section of the tapered SU-8 waveguide along with the electric field distribution of the supported TM photonic mode, (f) cross section of the aluminum plasmonic waveguide with the fabricated dimensions along with the electric field distribution of the fundamental plasmonic mode supported by the metal-SU-8 interface (bottom mode) in air and water conditions and the fundamental TM plasmonic mode supported by the metal - air and metal-water interfaces (top mode).

of the reference arm. Plasmonic mode excitation is obtained by launching a fundamental TM photonic mode in the input SU-8 photonic WG, which splits into two constituents and excites the two respective plasmonic modes when entering the metallic stripe. These two modes propagate along the two respective metal surfaces and interfere at the output photonic WG, realizing in this way a single-arm interferometer.

The sensing mechanism is based on the detection of refractive index (RI) changes in the liquid sample that comes on top of the metallic waveguide and fills the sensing area. This RI change induces a phase change on the highly sensitive SPP mode that propagates at the top surface of the stripe (top mode). The interferometer translates this phase change into a wavelength shift at the interferometer output.

The photonic waveguide platform consists of an uncladded $1.8 \mu\text{m} \times 1.5 \mu\text{m}$ (thickness \times width) SU-8 core ($n_{\text{SU-8}} = 1.575 - 0.0001j$) that lies on top of a $3 \mu\text{m}$ thick silicon oxide (SiO_2) substrate, with its cross-section depicted in Figure 1(d) along with the supported TM photonic mode profile. The stripe-based plasmonic waveguide is formed by an $80 \text{ nm} \times 7 \mu\text{m}$ aluminum ($n_{\text{Al}} = 1.427 - 15.135j$) [22] stripe that resides on top of an appropriately thinner SU-8 layer with the same width. In the following design approach, water ($n_{\text{water}} = 1.311 - 0.0001348j$) [23] was considered to form the over cladding. The cross-section geometry of the Al-on-SU-8 waveguide along with the mode profiles of the bottom and top plasmonic modes both in air and water condition are shown in Figure 1(f).

Design analysis

The goal of the design process is to maximize the sensitivity to bulk refractive index changes and to maximize the extinction ratio (ER) at the sensor output while minimizing overall losses. Towards this direction, the first step is to maximize the coupling efficiency from the photonic to the plasmonic part. To this end, the $1.8 \mu\text{m} \times 1.5 \mu\text{m}$ SU-8 stripe WG was linearly tapered to a $7 \mu\text{m}$ wide photonic WG prior reaching the plasmonic segment to provide a photonic mode (Figure 1(e)) that is spatially matched with the plasmonic modes supported by the Al stripe.

Figure 2. (Left axis) Overlap integral values between the TM photonic mode supported by the tapered SU-8 WG and (i) the top plasmonic mode (full black rectangle marker) and (ii) the bottom plasmonic mode (empty black rectangle marker) with respect to the bottom SU-8 layer thickness. (Right axis) Propagation losses for (i) the top mode (full blue rectangle) and (ii) the bottom mode (empty blue rectangle).

The second step concerns the optimization of the ER at the sensor output to allow for improved sensing properties with lower detection limits. The ER is defined as:

$$ER = 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{T_{\max}}{T_{\min}} \right) \quad (1)$$

where T_{\max} and T_{\min} represent the maximum (peak) and minimum (dip) values of the power at the interferometer output, respectively. We can obtain these values starting from the bimodal interferometric transfer function that gives the expected electric field at the output according to the following equation:

$$E_{out} = t_{01} e^{-j\beta_1 L} t_{10} + t_{02} e^{-j\beta_2 L} t_{20} \quad (2)$$

where t_{01} , t_{02} are the electric field coupling coefficients from the photonic tapered mode (0) to the top (1) and bottom (2) plasmonic modes respectively, t_{10} , t_{20} are the electric field coupling coefficient from the top and bottom plasmonic modes to the photonic tapered mode, L is the plasmonic length, and β_1 , β_2 are the corresponding propagation constants of top and bottom plasmonic modes, i.e., $\beta_i = (2\pi/\lambda_0)(n_i - jk_i)$ with n_i , k_i the real and imaginary parts of the complex effective index.

Assuming that there is no mode conversion on the plasmonic stripe, we can set:

$$t_{10} = t_{01} \text{ and } t_{20} = t_{02}$$

equation (2) is simplified as:

$$E_{out} = |t_1|^2 e^{-j\beta_1 L} + |t_2|^2 e^{-j\beta_2 L} \quad (3)$$

where $|t_1|^2 = t_{01} \cdot t_{10}$ and $|t_2|^2 = t_{02} \cdot t_{20}$ now represent the coupling coefficients from the input photonic tapered mode to the two plasmonic modes and back.

Considering that $T_{\max(\min)} = |E_{\max(\min)}|^2$, and that $E_{\max(\min)}$ is obtained when the two waves are in-phase, i.e., $L\Delta n/\lambda_0 = \text{integer}$ (off-phase, i.e., $L\Delta n/\lambda_0 = \text{half integer}$), then

$$T_{\max(\min)} = \left(|t_1|^2 \cdot e^{-a_1 L/2} \pm |t_2|^2 \cdot e^{-a_2 L/2} \right)^2 \quad (4)$$

where $a_i = 4\pi k_i/\lambda_0$, $i=1,2$ are the corresponding absorption coefficients and the sign $+$ ($-$) is used for the \max (\min) values.

Figure 3. Theoretical ER values for different thicknesses of the bottom SU-8 layer and for different plasmonic lengths.

Table 1. Summary of the theoretical results.

Al Length (μm)	FSR (nm)	Opt. bottom Su8 thickness (μm)	ER (dB)	Total losses (dB)
25	336.9	0.74	12	5.0
50	168.4	0.75	13	6.9
75	112.3	0.75	14.2	8.7
100	84.1	0.76	15.7	10.1
125	67.2	0.78	17.8	11.5
150	56.0	0.78	20.7	12.8
175	48.1	0.78	25	17.3

Since the two plasmonic modes have different propagation losses, optimal interference and, thus, ER can be achieved by tuning the coupling coefficients from the photonic to the two plasmonic modes in combination with the appropriate plasmonic stripe length. Coupling coefficients can be adjusted by varying the thickness of the bottom SU-8 layer. Towards this direction, a systematic 2D eigenmode analysis took place including (i) a detailed overlap integral analysis between the tapered TM photonic mode and the two plasmonic modes and (ii) the calculation of the propagation losses of the top and bottom plasmonic modes, both as a function of the bottom SU-8 layer thickness. Through overlap analysis, an estimation of the power fraction that can be transferred from the photonic mode to the two plasmonic modes (i.e. $|t_1|^2$ and $|t_2|^2$) can be obtained. The results of the above eigenmode analysis are presented in Figure 2. More specifically, the left axis of Figure 2 depicts the calculated overlap integral values while the right axis of the same figure shows the propagation losses of the top and bottom plasmonic modes as a function of the bottom SU-8 thickness. In specific, when the bottom SU-8 layer thickness varies between 0.7 μm and 1.15 μm , the plasmonic losses for the top mode range between 0.10 dB/ μm and 0.058 dB/ μm whilst the plasmonic losses for the bottom mode vary between 0.106 dB/ μm and 0.086 dB/ μm . Having determined the coupling coefficients from the overlap integrals and the plasmonic propagation losses, we proceed to the calculation of the ER by means of equations (1) for different SU-8 thicknesses and for plasmonic lengths ranging from 10 to 200 μm with a step size of 10 μm . The obtained results are presented in the contour plot in Figure 3. In addition, Table 1 summarizes the optimum

Figure 5. (a) Optical microscope image of the input SU-8 photonic waveguide before dicing and (b) magnified view of the Al plasmonic stripe waveguides.

Figure 6. Simulated transfer function across wavelength of the optimum bimodal sensor configuration having a 175 μm long Al plasmonic stripe on top of a 0.78 μm thick bottom SU-8 layer.

bottom SU-8 thickness that leads to a maximum ER for specific plasmonic lengths varying from 25 μm to 175 μm with a step of 25 μm along with the expected free spectral range (FSR) of each configuration and the total insertion losses of the device. The FSR was determined by means of the following equation:

$$FSR = \frac{\lambda^2}{\Delta n_g \cdot L} \quad (5)$$

where Δn_g is the difference between the group indices of the two plasmonic modes and L is the length of the Al plasmonic stripe. Through the above design analysis, the optimum bottom SU-8 layer thickness is equal to 0.78 μm resulting in an ER of 25 dB for a 175 μm long sensor. For the above configuration, the propagation losses are 0.076 dB/ μm for the top mode and

Figure 4. (a) Schematic of the experimental setup, (b) photo from the probe station used for optical characterization.

Figure 7. Fiber-to-fiber loss measurements versus wavelength for different plasmonic lengths in air. (a) 125 μm sensors, (b) 100 μm sensors, (c) 75 μm sensors and (d) 50 μm sensors.

0.102 dB/ μm for the bottom mode while the plasmonic photonic interface coupling losses are ~ 1 dB/interface. The complete interferometer was also evaluated via circuit-level simulations by using the INTERCONNECT photonic integrated circuit simulator of Lumerical. The frequency-dependent material properties and the waveguide dispersion were also taken into account. Figure 5 depicts the spectral response from the overall designed bimodal sensor, which exhibits an FSR of 42.6 nm.

Fabrication

The fabrication of the plasmo-photonic integrated sensor started with oxidizing 6" silicon wafers up to 3.0 μm SiO_2 thickness. The first SU-8 layer was then spin coated on the entire wafer followed by a two-stage soft-bake process on hot-plates. After an exposure in a Canon i5 i-line stepper tool, the wafer was developed in PGMEA solution. The deposition and exposure parameters were based on recommendations from the manufacturer. After development, a hard-bake step was performed on the wafer to fully cross-link the resist and form the first layer of the SU-8 waveguide stack (bottom SU-8 layer)

Table 2. Theoretical and experimental FSR values for sensors with Al stripe lengths of 125, 100, 75 and 50 μm in air.

Al Length (μm)	FSR theoretical (nm)	FSR experimental (nm)
125_1	31.45	35.8
125_2	31.45	34.8
100_1	39.31	42.2
100_2	39.31	42.5
75_1	52.42	59.4
75_2	52.42	55.1
50_1	78.63	93.3
50_2	78.63	88.7

Figure 8. Comparison between the simulated and experimental ER values for identical neighboring plasmonic sensors with Al stripe lengths of 125, 100, 75 and 50 in air.

which was measured equal to 0.9 μm thickness. For fabrication of the plasmonic stripe waveguide, an 80 nm thick Al layer was deposited on top of the bottom SU-8 layer using a sputter deposition process. The metal layer was patterned using i-line lithography and wet-etching. The result of the metal patterning step is Al plasmonic stripes of varying lengths formed atop the bottom SU-8 layer. Each plasmonic length was fabricated twice per die to check the repeatability of the fabrication process. This was followed by stacking the second (top) layer of SU-8 WG using the same process flow as described above. However, the deposition and exposure parameters were optimized to accommodate the topography generated after the first SU-8 layer. Images of the resulting devices are depicted in Figure 4(a) and (b), respectively. The final step was dicing of the wafer into 2 cm \times 2 cm chips. The end facet of the SU-8 waveguide layer stack required for butt-coupling was produced by a dicing saw. The saw feed rate and blade grit size were optimized to produce a reasonably smooth end facet in the SU-8 waveguide stack.

Experimental results

The experimental setup used for the optical characterization of the fabricated chips is depicted in Figure 6. A lensed polarization maintaining (PM) fiber connected to a tunable laser source

Table 3. Theoretical and experimental FSR values for sensors with Al stripe lengths of 150, 125, 100, 75, 50 and 25 μm in air and water.

Al Length (μm)	FSR theoretical (nm)		FSR experimental (nm)	
	Air	Water	Air	Water
150	26.2	61.2	28.8	58.4
125	31.4	73.5	32.5	74.1
100	39.3	91.9	47.1	98.8
75	52.4	122.5	53.9	-
50	78.6	183.8	76.7	-
25	157.2	367.7	-	-

Figure 9. (a) A water drop on top of the chip and (b) magnified view from the microscope showing the water drop above the plasmonic structures.

(TLS) was used to inject TM polarized light into the SU-8 waveguides via a butt coupling scheme. After propagation in the plasmophotonic structures, the light was collected via a single mode fiber (SMF) at the output of the chip and fed to an optical power meter (OPM) for interrogation. To facilitate the characterization process, the experimental setup also includes optomechanical components (stages, piezoelectric controllers, fiber holders, fiber rotators), a vacuum chip holder, a vacuum pump and a stereoscopic microscope equipped with both visible and infrared (IR) cameras. Broadband measurements were performed by sweeping the wavelength of the TLS from 1500 nm to 1630 nm with a resolution of 100 pm. In the first step, optical characterization was performed when the plasmonic WGs were exposed to air.

After the establishment of the optical link in the reference SU-8 WG, the plasmophotonic structures were characterized. Figure 7 presents the clear bimodal interferometric spectrum of sensors with plasmonic lengths of 125, 100, 75 and 50 μm . A fast Fourier transform fitting (FFT) was applied to the data of each spectrum to better follow the evolution of the sensors as described also in [24]. In each graph, the normalized spectra of two identical neighboring bimodal structures are given which match between the experimentally measured FSR and the

expected value from the simulation which verifies the bimodal as shown, are similar in all cases. Additionally, there is a clear functionality. The FSR values are summarized in Table 2. Plasmonic propagation losses were calculated utilizing equations (4) and (5) where the experimental T_{max} and T_{min} values were substituted and found equal to 0.10 dB/ μm for the top mode and 0.143 dB/ μm for the bottom mode. Accordingly, the photonic-plasmonic interface losses were found equal to 2.28 dB using the same set of equations. The above values are in quite good agreement with the simulation results, i.e. propagation losses of 0.055 dB/ μm for the top mode and 0.104 dB/ μm for the bottom mode, and interface losses of 2 dB per interface, considering the fabricated bottom SU-8 layer thickness (0.9 μm) and air cladding. Finally, the device was simulated with INTERCONNECT incorporating the experimental propagation and interface losses. Figure 8 illustrates the obtained results in terms of ER in comparison with the two experimental values corresponding to neighboring sensors with the same Al length for the above set of Al stripe lengths. Since the theoretical model builds upon the assumption that the photonic-to-plasmonic coupling coefficients at the sensor input are identical to the plasmonic-to-photonic coupling coefficients at the sensor output possible errors and inaccuracies during the fabrication process between the targeted and fabricated dimensions of the structure can affect the performance of the sensor. However, according to Figure 8 as the plasmonic stripe length is increasing, the ER of the sensor also increases, as it was expected from theory (the blue triangles in the graph).

Afterwards, the under investigation bimodal sensors were characterized in water condition by injecting a drop of water on the chip, as it can be seen in Figure 9(a) and (b). Figure 10 depicts the obtained spectra for six different plasmonic stripe lengths, i.e. 150, 125, 100, 75, 50 and 25 μm , along with the respective ones without the drop of water (air condition). The interference pattern between the air and water condition is different because water is lossy and thus we expect to observe

Figure 10. Fiber-to-fiber loss measurements versus wavelength in both air and water for: (a) 150 μm , (b) 125 μm , (c) 100 μm , (d) 75 μm , (e) 50 μm and (f) 25 μm long bimodal plasmonic stripes.

Figure 11. (a) Experimental sensor spectral response utilizing a 100 μm long Al stripe when using four different solutions with refractive index varying from 1.3320 to 1.3377. Measured experimental sensitivity: $S_{\text{exp}} = 4386 \text{ nm/RIU}$, (b) Equivalent simulated bimodal spectral response and sensitivity measurements of the same 100 μm long sensor. Simulated sensitivity: $S_{\text{sim}} = 5806 \text{ nm/RIU}$, (c) Linear fit on the resonance shift versus the changes in R.I. for the experimental spectra for two different cases, when the effective indexes change is equal with 0.0049, sensor 1 (red circles) and equal to 0.0114, sensor 2 (blue triangle) and for simulated spectra.

higher overall losses in water condition. It is clearly observed that for all plasmonic lengths there is a change in the spectrum response from air to water condition as it was expected from theory regarding, for example, the FSR values. This change in FSR values is caused due to the different refractive indices from air to water conditions. The expected changes of the FSR values are summarized in Table 3 for both air- and water-cladded sensor waveguides, clearly showing the matching between theory and experiment.

As can be seen, it was not possible to extract the FSR values for the sensor with 25 μm long plasmonic stripe in air and for the sensors with plasmonic lengths of 75, 50 and 25 μm in water condition because they are bigger than our observation window, the range of which is from 1500 nm to 1630 nm.

After the proof of principle experiments, the proposed bimodal sensing device was evaluated as an R.I. sensor. In particular, a sensor with 100 μm long plasmonic stripe was selected for evaluation since its FSR value is within the available spectral window. Sensitivity measurements were performed by injecting droplets of 4 different solutions with varying refractive indices ranging from 1.3359 to 1.3408 onto the sensing area. The RIs of the samples were defined by means a commercial refractometer. Figure 11(a) depicts the measured sensor spectra after applying the FFT filter for each solution revealing a clear blue shift of the resonance dip with increasing RI values. Figure 11 (b) presents the corresponding simulation curves. Bulk sensitivity values were calculated by performing least-squares linear fitting on the wavelength dip shift versus the refractive index change, as displayed in Figure 11 (c). Using this method, the achieved experimental bulk RI sensitivity was found equal to 4386 nm/RIU which is in very good agreement with the corresponding value of 5806 nm/RIU that was expected from simulation. The sensor performance was also evaluated over a wider RI range using another bimodal sensor (sensor 2) in order to better evaluate its linear dynamic range. A set of different liquids with a RI value within the range 1.3329 to 1.3443 was utilized, with the respective sensitivity results included in Fig. 11(c) and revealing an almost identical performance with sensor 1. Apart from the bulk sensitivity, the waveguide surface sensitivity was also calculated assuming a protein adlayer above the plasmonic waveguide with a refractive index of 1.48 [25] and thickness varying from 10 nm to 50 nm with step of 10 nm. After performing 2D eigenmode simulations, the surface waveguide sensitivity of the top mode was found equal to 0.0001488 RIU/nm according to the equation:

$$S_s = \frac{\delta n_{\text{eff}}}{\delta t} \quad (6)$$

where n_{eff} represents the effective index of the top plasmonic mode waveguide and t is the thickness of the extra layer.

We also calculated the whole sensor surface sensitivity considering the following cases: (i) plasmonic stripe in water ($n_{\text{water}}=1.311$) without any other layer on top (reference measurement), (ii) plasmonic stripe with a 20 nm- thick protein adlayer (with $n=1.48$). The above investigation revealed a sensor surface sensitivity of 99 nm/RIU. In order to validate the sensitivity measurements, we repeated the sensing experiment for 3 different sensors with plasmonic length of 100 μm and the obtained sensitivities were calculated equal to 4386 nm/RIU, 4405 nm/RIU and 4464 nm/RIU, respectively. To further evaluate the performance of the proposed plasmo-photonic sensor another important metric is the limit of detection (LOD). According to [26], the LOD is the minimum refractive index change that can be accurately detected from the readout system and is defined with the following equation:

$$\text{LoD} = \frac{R}{\text{Sensitivity}} \quad (7)$$

where R is the smallest possible spectral shift that can be accurately measured. The resolution of the tunable laser used for the sensitivity measurements is 0.0001 nm. Accounting system noise, we assume a lowest detectable wavelength change equal to 0.01 nm resulting in a LoD of 10^{-6} RIU.

Conclusion

We have developed a novel, ultra-compact refractive index sensor based on a CMOS compatible metal stripe, co-integrated for the first time on a SU-8 photonic waveguide platform, exploiting the advantages offered by SU-8. The plasmonic waveguide has been designed to support two SPP modes at the two metal/insulator interfaces (top and bottom) which upon excitation can interfere at the output waveguide forming a single-arm interferometer, known as bimodal configuration, reducing by this way the total footprint of the sensor since there is only one physical branch. Through this configuration we manage to obtain the highest bulk sensitivity value among all bimodal sensors using CMOS compatible metal. Specifically, we experimentally measured bulk sensitivities up to 4464 nm/RIU for

Table 4. A comparison table with some reported bimodal sensors regarding the sensitivity and the LoD.

Ref.	Type	Sensitivity (nm/RIU)	LoD (RIU)
[3]	MZI (plasmonic)	488	1.5×10^{-5}
[16]	Bimodal (plasmo-photonic)	-	10^{-6}
[17]	Bimodal (plasmo-photonic)	315	-
[18]	Bimodal (plasmo-photonic)	2430	-
[27]	Bimodal (Polymer platform)	789	-
This work	Bimodal (plasmonic)	4386	10^{-6}

three sensors with 100 μm long aluminum stripes which was also confirmed by simulations. As can be seen from Table 4 the proposed sensor is a tangible example of the benefits offered when the high-sensitivity capabilities of plasmonics get combined with the low-loss and low-cost SU-8 photonic platform in compact, low-cost and ultra-sensitive interferometric sensing devices.

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